

FEATURES OF DIASTOLIC DYSFUNCTION IN PATIENTS WITH ISCHAEMIC HEART DISEASE SUFFERING FROM TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS**Alyavi A.***Doctor of Medical Sciences, Academician, Head of the Cardiology Laboratory at the Republican Specialised Scientific and Practical Medical Centre for Therapy and Medical Rehabilitation***Nazarova G.***Junior Researcher at the Republican Specialised Scientific and Practical Medical Centre for Therapy and Medical Rehabilitation***Tulyaganova D.***Doctor of Medical Sciences, Head of the Cardiology Department of the Republican Specialised Scientific and Practical Medical Centre for Therapy and Medical Rehabilitation***Khan T.***Junior Researcher at the Republican Specialised Scientific and Practical Medical Centre for Therapy and Medical Rehabilitation***Yakubov M.***Senior Researcher at the Republican Specialised Scientific and Practical Medical Centre for Therapy and Medical Rehabilitation***Rajabova D.***Junior Researcher at the Republican Specialised Scientific and Practical Medical Centre for Therapy and Medical Rehabilitation***Toshev B.***Junior Researcher at the Republican Specialised Scientific and Practical Medical Centre for Therapy and Medical Rehabilitation***Abstract**

Mortality from cardiovascular diseases (CVD) worldwide exceeds 17 million people per year, accounting for approximately one-third of all deaths and remaining the leading cause of mortality in many countries. Endothelial dysfunction (ED) is an important pathogenetic link in the development and progression of IHD and type 2 diabetes mellitus. ED is defined as an imbalance between the production of vasodilatory, antiproliferative factors (NO, prostacyclin, tissue plasminogen activator, etc.) and vasoconstrictive, prothrombotic, proliferative factors (endothelin-1, superoxide anion, thromboxane A₂, etc.).

Keywords: coronary heart disease, sulodexide, endothelial dysfunction.

Introduction. Mortality from cardiovascular diseases (CVD) worldwide exceeds 17 million people per year, accounting for approximately one-third of all deaths and remaining the leading cause of mortality in many countries [1]. According to official statistics, the Republic of Uzbekistan is also among the regions with a high risk of developing CVD: in 2019, the proportion of deaths from non-communicable diseases exceeded 83.5% (702.8 per 100,000 population), with CVD accounting for 60.3% of total mortality [2]. In subsequent years (2021 data), the cumulative proportion of deaths related to CVD remained high at 61.7% (107,666 out of a total of 174,500 registered deaths), with mortality among men aged 18–74 being twice as high as that among women [3].

Interest in the treatment and prevention of IHD is due to the high prevalence of this disease and its leading role in the structure of disability and mortality among the population, which gives this problem not only medical but also socio-economic significance [4–6]. At the same time, there has been a steady increase in the number of patients with diabetes mellitus (DM), primarily type 2, which is considered a socially significant disease due to the high frequency of macro- and microvascular complications [7]. Type 2 diabetes is one of the key risk factors for the development of IHD; when combined, the prognostic significance of complications increases.

Endothelial dysfunction (ED) is an important pathogenetic link in the development and progression of IHD and type 2 diabetes mellitus. ED is defined as an imbalance between the production of vasodilatory, antiproliferative factors (NO, prostacyclin, tissue plasminogen activator, etc.) and vasoconstrictive, prothrombotic, proliferative factors (endothelin-1, superoxide anion, thromboxane A₂, etc.) [8–10]. The leading role in the pathogenesis of ED belongs to a decrease in the bioavailability of endothelial nitric oxide (NO), activation of endothelin-1, and an imbalance of vascular endothelial growth factors (VEGF) [8–10]. In addition, in the early stages of diabetes development, an important role is played by impaired synthesis of heparan sulphate, a glycosaminoglycan (GAG) that is part of the basement membrane and forms the active surface layer of the endothelium; GAG deficiency leads to impaired vascular wall permeability and structural and functional changes in the tissue [11,12].

Sulodexide, a member of the glycosaminoglycan group (a combination of a heparin-like fraction and dermatan sulphate), has angioprotective, antithrombotic and profibrinolytic activity, restores the charge and structure of the glycocalyx and basement membrane, and modulates fibrinolysis and anti-inflammatory pathways [12–14]. In this regard, it is advisable to study the effect of sulodexide on markers of endothelial dysfunction in patients with IHD and concomitant type 2 diabetes mellitus.

The aim of the study is to evaluate the effect of sulodexide (Vessel Due F) on the state of endothelial dysfunction in patients with ischaemic heart disease with concomitant type 2 diabetes mellitus.

Materials and methods. The study included 115 patients diagnosed with IHD, functional class II exertional angina, and a history of myocardial revascularisation. Inclusion criteria: stable angina pectoris of functional class II, previous coronary revascularisation, age >18 years, informed consent. Exclusion criteria: acute myocardial infarction or unstable angina in the previous 3 months, severe renal or hepatic insufficiency, cancer, use of drugs affecting the levels of the studied markers outside of standard therapy.

Patients were divided into groups based on the presence of diabetes mellitus: Group 1 (IHD without diabetes mellitus) — 59 patients; Group 2 (IHD with type 2 diabetes mellitus) — 56 patients;

Control group — 20 practically healthy individuals who had no signs of cardiovascular pathology at the time of the study.

Anthropometric measurements (height, body weight, body mass index — BMI) were taken for the entire contingent, heart rate and blood pressure were recorded, and general clinical and biochemical tests were performed: total cholesterol (TC), HDL cholesterol, LDL cholesterol, triglycerides (TG), creatinine, fibrinogen, urea, and estimated glomerular filtration rate (CKD-EPI formula).

To assess the condition of the endothelium, circulating markers were determined: endothelin-1 (ET-1),

vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), interleukin-6 (IL-6) and D-dimer. Measurements were performed using solid-phase enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) with commercial kits: VEGF-IFA-BEST (Vector-Best, Russia) — measurement range 6.25–4000 pg/ml for VEGF, Elabscience kits (USA) — for ET-1 (reference range 4.0–36.3 pg/ml), etc. Reference ranges were used according to test kit manufacturers and clinical recommendations.

Patients were prescribed sulodexide (Vessel Due F) at a dose of 250 IU twice daily (orally) for 6 months in addition to standard therapy for IHD and DM, which included antianginal, antihypertensive, hypolipidemic, and hypoglycemic drugs as indicated. In 70 patients (34 from the IHD with diabetes mellitus group and 36 from the IHD without diabetes mellitus group), blood samples were taken again after 6 months of therapy to study the dynamics of ED markers.

Statistical analysis was performed using standard methods: indicators are presented as mean ± standard deviation (M±SD). Student's t-test for independent and related samples was used to compare the groups; differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$. Significance levels are indicated in the text and tables.

Results. Initial clinical and biochemical characteristics

The groups were comparable in terms of age, BMI, and haemodynamic parameters at the time of inclusion (Table 1). In the IHD with SD group, higher blood glucose levels and a tendency towards higher TG and fibrinogen levels were observed, as expected.

Table 1

Clinical characteristics of patients in both groups

Index	CHD non DM (n=59)	CHD DM (n=56)
Age, year	68,9 ± 7,47	68,3 ± 7,71
BMI, kg/m ²	29,9 ± 0,4	30,11 ± 0,75
HR, per min	81 ± 14	83 ± 13
SBP, mmHg	138 ± 19	143 ± 7
DBP, mmHg	82 ± 8	85 ± 4
Glucose, mmol/l	5,41 ± 0,12	8,5 ± 0,41 *
Total cholesterol, mmol/l	4,83 ± 0,42	4,95 ± 0,30
HDL, mmol/l	1,39 ± 0,06	1,35 ± 0,064
LDL, mmol/l	2,52 ± 0,33	2,79 ± 0,227
TG, mmol/l	2,67 ± 0,51	2,93 ± 0,32 *
Fibrinogen, g/l	345,39 ± 26,96	394,82 ± 12,11
Urea, mmol/l	6,54 ± 0,41	7,63 ± 0,75
GFR, ml/min/1,73 m ² (CKD-EPI)	71,9 ± 25,8	68,7 ± 20,9

* — $p < 0,05$ when compared with the group without diabetes mellitus.

When comparing the baseline levels of ED markers in patients from both main groups and the control group, significant differences were found (Table 2). Patients with IHD and DM had significantly higher levels

of ET-1, VEGF, and IL-6 compared to patients with IHD without DM and the control group; D-dimer levels were also elevated compared to the control group.

Table 2

Baseline levels of endothelin-1, VEGF, IL-6, and D-dimer in patients with CHD

Index	CHD non DM (n=59)	CHD with DM (n=56)	Control group (n=20)
Endotelin-1, pg/ml	49,97 ± 3,41	86,15 ± 7,52	16,94 ± 1,71
VEGF, pg/ml	800,13 ± 38,43	1050,15 ± 49,85	241,88 ± 27,87
IL-6, pg/ml	27,58 ± 2,92	41,40 ± 4,16	13,35 ± 1,29
D-dimer, ng/ml	287,61 ± 47,77	292,42 ± 35,86	124,85 ± 21,24

Intergroup differences between groups I (IHD without SD) and II (IHD with SD) in ET-1, VEGF, and IL-6 were statistically significant ($p < 0.001$ for ET-1 and VEGF, $p \approx 0.001$ for IL-6). The differences in D-dimer levels between the patient groups were less pronounced ($p \approx 0.05$ when compared with the control group).

The entire cohort was prescribed sulodexide at a dose of 250 IU twice daily for 6 months. Repeat blood sampling after 6 months was performed in 70 patients (34 from the IHD with SD group and 36 from the IHD without SD group). Analysis of the dynamics of the indicators demonstrated a significant decrease in the levels of all studied markers in patients who underwent a follow-up examination (Table 3).

Table 3

Changes in ET-1, VEGF, IL-6, and D-dimer levels during sulodexide therapy

Index	CHD non DM c CД (before, n=56)	CHD with DM (before, n=59)	CHD with DM (after, n=34)	CHD non DM (after, n=36)
Endothelin-1, pg/ml	86,15 ± 7,52	49,97 ± 3,41	48,69 ± 4,05 *	33,84 ± 3,08 *
VEGF, pg/ml	1050,15 ± 49,85	800,13 ± 38,43	683,33 ± 39,15 *	673,10 ± 36,64 *
IL-6, pg/ml	41,40 ± 4,16	27,58 ± 2,92	25,34 ± 2,84 *	19,87 ± 2,41 *
D-dimer, ng/ml	292,42 ± 35,86	287,61 ± 47,77	171,51 ± 21,29 *	172,67 ± 22,34 *

* — $p < 0,05$ compared with baseline values (before treatment) in the corresponding group.

As shown in Table 3, after a 6-month course of sulodexide, patients who underwent repeat tests showed a statistically significant decrease in ET-1, VEGF, IL-6, and D-dimer levels. At the same time, the absolute values after treatment in the IHD with SD group remained higher than in the group without SD, but the intergroup differences after therapy decreased and became statistically insignificant for a number of indicators (in particular, the difference in ET-1 between the groups after treatment was insignificant, $p \approx 0.10$ in the initial calculation data).

Discussion. This study shows that patients with IHD and concomitant type 2 diabetes mellitus have pronounced endothelial dysfunction, which manifests itself in significantly increased levels of ET-1, VEGF, and IL-6. These data are fully consistent with the modern concept of the pathogenesis of vascular complications in diabetes mellitus: hyperglycaemia and insulin resistance induce oxidative stress, enhance the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines, and activate tissue pathways leading to a decrease in NO bioavailability and activation of vasoconstrictor factors (endothelin-1). Elevated VEGF reflects reactive angiogenesis and permeability activity in response to vascular wall damage [8–11].

Elevated IL-6 in the SD group confirms the presence of a systemic inflammatory response and correlates with the intensity of vascular damage. D-dimer, as a marker of coagulation and fibrinolysis activation, was also higher in patients compared to controls, indicating

an increased thrombotic potential in the study population.

The administration of sulodexide for 6 months was accompanied by a significant reduction in the levels of all markers studied in both patients with diabetes mellitus and patients without diabetes. These results indicate the multifaceted pharmacodynamic effects of the drug: restoration of the structural and functional properties of the glycocalyx and basement membrane, reduction of prothrombotic activity (including effects on factor Xa and thrombin), enhancement of fibrinolytic activity (stimulation of tissue plasminogen activator secretion) and reduction in the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines [12–14]. A decrease in ET-1 levels during sulodexide therapy may indicate restoration of endothelial control of vascular tone and a decrease in vasoconstrictor load, while a decrease in VEGF and IL-6 may indicate a decrease in the inflammatory and permeability components of the vascular response.

Comparison with literature data: in a number of clinical and experimental studies, sulodexide has shown the ability to improve microcirculation, normalise vascular wall permeability and reduce markers of inflammation in patients with diabetes mellitus and vascular complications; our results are consistent with these observations [12–14]. At the same time, the literature notes variability in the effect depending on the initial severity of vascular damage, the duration and dose of therapy, as well as concomitant drug therapy, which should be taken into account when interpreting the results.

The clinical significance of the data obtained is that correction of GAG deficiency and restoration of the glycocalyx structure using sulodexide can be considered as an additional therapeutic strategy in the combination of IHD and type 2 diabetes mellitus to reduce endothelial dysfunction, reducing the inflammatory response and thrombotic risk, which in the long term may lead to a reduction in clinical complications and an improved prognosis.

In conclusion, it should be noted that patients with IHD and concomitant type 2 diabetes mellitus have more pronounced endothelial dysfunction compared to patients with IHD without diabetes mellitus and practically healthy individuals (increased levels of ET-1, VEGF, IL-6, and D-dimer).

A course of therapy with sulodexide (Vessel Due F) at 250 IU twice daily for 6 months was accompanied by a significant decrease in ED marker levels (ET-1, VEGF, IL-6, D-dimer) in both patients with and without diabetes.

The data obtained confirm the promise of including sulodexide in the complex therapy of patients with IHD and type 2 diabetes mellitus for the correction of endothelial dysfunction and a potential reduction in the risk of vascular complications. Large-scale randomised studies are needed to confirm the clinical effect and impact on outcomes.

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